

POLITICAL SCIENCES

MEXICO IN THE SEARCH FOR THE CONSTRUCTION OF A PUBLIC POLICY ON THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

This work explores Mexico's environmental efforts from a federal perspective. Theoretically it is based on the idea that there is a need to act as a group to benefit the interest of the members, which in this case are all the government actors that are involved in environmental issues and are contrasted with the approaches of national development plans to identify in which six-year periods emphasis has been given to the treatment of problems that affect the environment. Although policies and government structures are identified, the decline in public interest has decreased in each political transition process in the last presidential six-year term.

Keywords: National plan, environment, political actors, environmental actions, government.

A scenario for transformation: 2030 agenda for Sustainable Development

Since the industrial revolution, a consumption system was developed that obeys liberal political ideas. Although it has its advantages, it has brought with it other types of consequences in the medium and long term, which are framed in both issues like economic as well as social but that are visualized in the environment. On the other hand, according to Olson (1965) it is considered that "on a larger scale, social classes often give rise to thinking that they would act in the interest of the members", which is why it has been thought that these features Marxist in liberal governments have sown the idea of the common good, which has not happened, but quite the opposite, as a result of this failed idea, the problem that has had the most impact has been a blow to the very survival of the human being, that is, that of the environment.

This can be explained in the following way, using an analogy with a public good such as a park or a street, although all the inhabitants of a certain community want to have beautiful parks and streets with good infrastructure, but what happens in the real life after daily use by hundreds or thousands of people is that when having to clean the park or the street, no one is willing to do it since no one of them is the particular owner,

and that is the most compelling characteristic of a public good, which "belongs to everyone and belongs to no one", however, even if it does not have a particular owner, it is up to the State to assume the task of cleaning, care and protection, which is not always achieved in all parks or in all the streets, since if this were not the case we would not have piles of garbage everywhere as well as potholes, abandoned parks among other elements that contaminate the visual image of our cities.

So, what happens in this scenario, "all the citizens of that community want to enjoy the park and the street" but "they do not want the responsibility of cleaning and care", then the same thing happens with the environment, everyone wants to enjoy a clean and healthy environment but they are not willing to generate actions to keep it clean and in good condition." In principle, it could be argued against what I say, that there are many environmental groups, that there is also an international environmental agenda, and in some cases in domestic politics, however, this does not mean that they are taking shape in actions or in concrete policies. In this sense, the data demonstrate that high levels of environmental pollution affect or put human life at risk, as shown as an example in the following map dated May 25, 2024.

Image 1.- Map showing air pollution in part of Africa, Saudi Arabia, India and China.
 Fuente: <https://www.ventusky.com/?p=35.3;71.8;3&l=pm25>

Where the most polluted places on the globe correspond to the Asian continents, part of the Middle East and Africa, in the case of Mexico, air pollution is concentrated in the center of the country, as shown in the following map. In general, it can be inferred that one of the factors that explain the high levels of pollution in the air that become harmful to health is the high concentration of the population in the same place associated with the concentration factor in industrialization,

that is, to larger the population, the higher the levels of pollution.

Although Mexico is a country that does not demonstrate the same severity of air pollution, compared to the places in the first image, it is also important to recognize that, having a large geographic territory, there are places where the concentration of the population is greater than in other cities, as happens in the cities surrounding the country's capital.

Image 2.-Map showing air pollution in the cities surrounding Mexico City, the country's capital.
 Fuente: <https://www.ventusky.com/?p=19.320;-99.226;9&l=pm10>

In this work, an analysis is carried out based on the literature on the logic of collective action, whose main methodological argument is the behavior of groups (Olson, 1985), starting from the idea that "on a larger scale, social classes frequently give rise to thinking that these

would act in the interest of the members", therefore it would be expected that there would be greater common interest in the environment, however this has not happened, which is why the following questions are raised:

What would be the group explanation? Why haven't environmental policies worked? Olson raises some elements that can contribute to the analysis of the problem. One of them is based on individual efforts and those who receive the profits, although in the struggle to obtain some benefit that translates into direct advantages through public services, for example, paving your street, providing you with water, energy, electricity, it is very likely that the majority participates in these social struggles, however, since these benefits have been earned, the need for participation decreases Why?

Perhaps because comforts have been obtained in modern times and those who later join that community did nothing and still benefit from those advantages, without having made any effort, since the gains are applied to all members (*Ibidem*) of the group. Due to this, in the following scheme a scheme of positive and negative selective incentives for actors involved in the problem is proposed, based on the following question: Should citizens-users of services participate in environmental care? And what role should the State play in the environmental protection scenario?

Scheme 1.-Global environmental positive and negative incentives

Source: self made

This scheme shows positive actions and negative actions represent incentives. These actions converge at one point, which is survival. It is necessary to combat problems that have been created globally from industrialization processes and intensified by globalization, economical. Although it is true in origin that economic liberalism allowed the emergence of the democracies of this century, as well as the advancement in the level of civility through the creation of relevant norms with social changes, it also allowed the free market to remain in the hands of large companies, leaving the Nation-States a regulatory and surveillance role, but the most shocking thing is that the new designs and handling of materials to bring the products closer to the population that uses them, meant and continues to mean great environmental costs. Even though these actions represent progress in urban development and the economy, the deterioration of the environment was not contemplated by what is now one of the greatest challenges of the 21st century. In this sense, even though these challenges we face continue to be about resources, the shift that has taken place is that the countries with the highest level of industrialization are also those with the highest urban concentration and therefore, they are the ones that they have more contamination, as demonstrated in the previous images.

In the case of Mexico, it is one of the countries that had no problems in recognizing that there are environ-

mental problems, in such a way that its regulation recognizes from the Constitution the need to consider the environment as a State policy, which is why it is easy to identify which government actors are tasked with generating actions that seek to reduce the problems associated with global warming. This does not mean that it is enough, however, it must be recognized that being one of the countries that is not qualified as a world power, is assumed as a good sign.

The following table shows the governmental and non-governmental actors that may have a direct relationship with the environmental issue, as well as the type of incentive, this can be positive or negative, being positive it is defined as one that will bring with it some type of benefit or improvement, whether in the short, medium or long term, as well as it will have a positive impact on the mitigation of the problem, while we understand negative as that which contributes to the growth of the environmental problem or that is not providing elements for the reduction of the same. Regarding the local actors, the federative entity of Baja California is taken as a reference case, and the two most important municipalities for the State, the first Mexicali, for being the seat of local powers and the municipality of Tijuana for being the border city with southern California, USA, and the city with the largest population, as well as the greatest social mobility in the State.

Table 1

Actors involved in environmental issues by level and type of incentive.

Niveles		Tipo de actor político-institucional	Tipo de incentivo
Federal		Secretaría de la Marina Secretaría de medio ambiente y recursos naturales Secretaría de energía Secretaría de economía Secretaría de educación pública Secretaría de Desarrollo Agrario, Territorial y Urbano; Secretaría de Cultura; Secretaría de Turismo Comisión Nacional del agua Comisión Nacional forestal	Positivo
Estatal		Secretaría de manejo, saneamiento y protección del agua Secretaría de pesca y acuicultura Secretaría de medio ambiente y desarrollo sustentable	Positivo
Municipal	Mexicali	Presidencia municipal Dirección de administración urbana Dirección de protección al medio ambiente Comité de planeación para el desarrollo municipal Consejo de urbanización municipal Fideicomiso para el Desarrollo Urbano Instituto municipal de investigación y planeación urbana Sistema municipal de transporte Comisiones: Comisión de Desarrollo Urbano y Control Ecológico Comisión de Planeación de Desarrollo Municipal Comisión de Seguridad Pública, Tránsito y Transporte Comisión de Obras y Servicios Públicos Comisión de Salud, Deporte y Recreación Comisión de Equidad de Género y Derechos Humanos Comisión de Desarrollo Rural Comisión de Educación, Cultura y Asuntos Indígenas Comisión de Desarrollo Económico, Turismo y Federalismo	Positivo
	Tijuana	Presidencia municipal Secretaría de movilidad urbana sustentable Secretaría de desarrollo económico Secretaría de educación Instituto municipal de arte y cultura Dirección de desarrollo social y municipal Instituto metropolitano de planeación Sistema municipal de parques temáticos de Tijuana Sistema integral de transporte de Tijuana Comisiones: Comisión de Gobernación, Legislación y Mejora Regulatoria Comisión de Planeación, Urbanismo, Obras y Servicios Públicos. Comisión de Desarrollo Metropolitano. Comisión de Medio Ambiente, Desarrollo Sustentable y Salud.	Positivo
Otros actores		Sector empresarial	Negativo/Positivo
		Sector agrícola,	Positivo/Negativo
		Recicladoras	Positivo/Negativo
		Empresas globales como Coca-cola, Pepsico, Amazon, McDonalds, Startbucks, Costco	Negativo/Positivo
		Organizaciones no gubernamentales	Positivo
		Organismos operadores del agua en Baja California	Negativo
		Comisión Federal de la Luz (CFE)	Negativo

Source: self made.

As can be seen in the previous table, positive incentives fall mainly on government actors, based on the principle that the State has the moral and legal power to create the conditions to generate elements that serve as an instrument to innovate in actions that mitigate the environmental problem. On the other hand, negative incentives fall mainly on other actors for various reasons. First, the business sector that has had and has strength from the formation and transition to the Liberal State, has consolidated itself as one of the sectors that have contributed the most to the problem of plastics, in principle by creating them and followed by innovation in their transportation for consumption by the population.

For their part, some have been marked as negative/positive, this is because, although they play an important role in the economy and development, they have also contributed widely to the creation of the problem, in some cases not only environmental but also health, (topic that will not be addressed). In the case of the recyclers, they were marked positive/negative because although the work they do is essential to promote rejection, on the other hand, the number of materials that can be recycled is very limited, and in the Mexican case they do not count with recyclers that promote a circular economy, but rather the best materials that are recycled are exported, while the materials that are not considered of value remain in Mexico, and that in the medium term contribute to solid waste pollution.

The agricultural sector is considered positive/negative, first because it plays a fundamental role in the survival of human beings by providing basic food supplies, but second because not all of the agricultural sector has implemented innovation schemes that allow savings in consumption of water. On the opposite side, there are two government actors that are considered negative and that have a great environmental impact, the first is the Federal Electricity Commission, being the only supplier of electrical energy in this country (even with the constitutional prohibition of monopolies) and that only in 2016 was the regulation approved that allows the participation of some individuals to provide the energy service with solar panels, charging a rate for it, the truth is that since it is a government company and lacks liberal competition, it does not It has made it possible to generate incentives for improvement, so that in summer or with the presence of meteorological phenomena, infrastructure failures are noticeable.

Likewise, with the operating organizations, known as state water commissions of Tijuana, Mexicali, Ensenada, etc., they are in charge of the administration of the management and distribution of water

and which have stood out in recent years for a low quality in the infrastructure to provide water and sanitation services.

International Agenda for the Protection and Care of the Global Environment

The environmental issue has been in the media discourses of the vast majority of high-level political actors for several decades now, alluding to the effective link with the declaration of the United Nations General Assembly, called "Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda." for Sustainable Development", where a set of objectives and goals are proposed which have the environment in common, mainly pointing out that they are determined "to protect the planet against degradation, including through sustainable consumption and production, sustainable management of its natural resources and urgent measures to address climate change, so that it can meet the needs of present and future generations" (UN, 2015).

In this sense, one of the most compelling arguments of the declaration is that "no one is left behind" and that it will seek to "reach those furthest behind first" so it is considered appropriate to present some of the main indicators in relation to the achievements, as well as the delays in environmental matters.

According to the latest UN report on the scope by country of the goals in the 2030 agenda, in goal 6 regarding water resources, Mexico is one of the countries that are in the scope scheme. limited in progress in the implementation of integrated water resources management 2017-2020.

Likewise, the trend of forest area as a proportion of the total area, 2015-2020, Mexico have the place the deterioration category, although our northern neighbors are only in the following category, with slight or no improvement, the countries to reach they are Australia, and some Europeans like Italy, and in Asia to China among others. In this sense, it should be noted that climate change, being a serious consequence that is made mostly visible by deforestation, requires joint actions that not only correspond to the Government as an actor, but also involve other actors as agents of change, mainly social.

In this sense, it is understood that the development objectives for the 2030 agenda are based on the awareness of the depletion of natural resources, as well as the degradation of the environment mainly due to drought, with climate change as the main consequence. However, although sustainable development is constantly found in discourses, in practice sufficient activities are not detected to support them. The following table shows the objectives specifically oriented to the environment.

Table 2

Goals of the UN 2030 agenda, with an environmental focus.

Goal	Description
2	End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture.
6	Ensure the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all.
11	Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.
12	Guarantee sustainable consumption and production patterns.
13	Adopt urgent measures to combat climate change and its effects*
14	Conserve and sustainably use oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.
15	Protect, restore and promote the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.

Source: UN

Derived from goal 13, strategy 13.2 emerged, which seeks to incorporate measures related to climate change in national policies, strategies and plans, in which countries commit to incorporating the measures into their domestic agendas. Now, how has Mexico fared in national politics, being one of the countries that have agreed with international pronouncements.

Mexico: from the development of the agenda towards the transformation of politics

Starting from a regulatory approach, in Mexico, the environmental issue has had an impact on its legal framework, which has origins since 1999, 16 years before the establishment of the 2030 agenda, however, the task had been pending since 1972 with the first world conference on the environment in Stockholm, in which 26 principles were established placing the environment in the foreground, later in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 the World Conference on Environment and Development was held, resulting in “*program 21*” highlighting the existence of an interdependence between economic aspects and environmental damage.

Subsequently, the General Assembly met in New York in 1997 as a five-year evaluation, and it was not until this last event that international influence took effect in Mexico, since at the end of this period under the leadership of President Ernesto Zedillo Ponce de León, On June 28, 1999, the modification was made to Article 4 of the Constitution, adding that “every person has the right to an environment adequate for their development and well-being.” From this moment on, it became a State policy, which implies that the Mexican State places the environment above partisan political pressures. This suggests tangible changes in the administrative structure at the federal level, which must be replicated in the parts that make up the federation, that is, in the federal entities.

The thirteenth constitutional reform of article 4 in Mexico on February 8, 2012, added the part of the individual's responsibility towards the environment,

making it subject to sanctions, as established in secondary regulations, in such a way that the article remained as follows “Every person has the right to a healthy environment for their development and well-being. The State will guarantee respect for this right. “Environmental damage and deterioration will generate liability for whoever causes it in terms of the provisions of the law.” Every person has the right to access, disposal and sanitation of water for personal and domestic consumption in a sufficient, healthy, acceptable and affordable manner. The State will guarantee this right and the law will define the bases, supports and modalities for the equitable and sustainable access and use of water resources, establishing the participation of the Federation, the federal entities and the municipalities, as well as the participation of citizens to the achievement of said purposes.”

And finally, in the reform of December 18, 2020, it was added to the 4th constitutional article that “Every person has the right to mobility in conditions of road safety, accessibility, efficiency, sustainability, quality, inclusion and equality.”

Therefore, in Mexico, as can be seen, the environmental issue becomes a State Policy, and it stands out that since 2012, the act of committing damage and deterioration for those who do not protect the environment is considered sanctions. Since it is incorporated in this constitutional article, being for the last reform, the concept of “sustainability” is included, which adds greater impact due to its discursive quality, however in the international reports by the “Climate Change Performance Index” it is not included. have identified strong advances for Mexico (See image # 3). The following table shows the regulatory instruments on environmental matters for Mexico and the most relevant aspects.

Table 3

Mexico: Secondary regulation in environmental matters shows the laws that were created to safeguard the environment.

Legal instrument	Creation date	Relevant aspects
Organic law of the federal public administration	December 29, 1976. Last reform DOF 01-12-2023.	Article 26 contemplates the creation for administrative office matters of the Secretary of the Environment and Natural Resources, as well as of Energy, Agriculture and Rural Development, Agrarian, Territorial and Urban Development.
General Law for the Prevention and Comprehensive Management of Waste	October 8, 2003. Last reform DOF 05-08-2023	It guarantees the right of every person to a healthy environment and promotes sustainable development through the prevention of the generation, recovery and comprehensive management of hazardous, mining and metallurgical waste, urban solids, special management; prevent the contamination of sites with these wastes and carry out their remediation.
General Law on Humanities, Sciences, Technologies and Innovation	May 8, 2023	It guarantees the exercise of the human right to science in accordance with the principles of universality, interdependence, indivisibility and progressivity, so that every person enjoys the benefits of the development of science and technological innovation, as well as human rights in general.
General Law of Ecological Balance and Environmental Protection	January 28, 1988. Last reform DOF 05-08-2023	Its objective is to promote sustainable development and establish the bases for: I.- Guarantee the right of every person to live in a healthy environment for their development, health and well-being; II.- Define the principles of environmental policy and the instruments for its application; III.- The preservation, restoration and improvement of the environment; IV.- The preservation and protection of biodiversity, as well as the establishment and administration of protected natural areas; V.- Sustainable use, preservation and restoration of soil, water and other natural resources, preservation of ecosystems; VI.- The prevention and control of air, water and soil pollution; VII.- Guarantee the co-responsible participation of people, individually or collectively, in the preservation and restoration of the ecological balance and the protection of the environment; VIII.- The exercise of the powers that in environmental matters correspond to the Federation, the federal entities, the Municipalities and the territorial demarcations of Mexico City, under the principle of concurrence provided for in Article 73 section XXIX – G of the Constitution ; Reformed fraction DOF 01-19-2018 IX.- The establishment of coordination, induction and consultation mechanisms between authorities, between them and academic and research institutions, the social and private sectors, as well as with people and social groups, in environmental matters; Reformed section DOF 04-11-2022 penalties that correspond
General Law of Sustainable Fishing and Aquaculture	July 24, 2007. Last reform DOF 01-19-2023	Its purpose is to regulate, promote and manage the use of fishing and aquaculture resources in the national territory and the areas over which the nation exercises its sovereignty and jurisdiction.
General Law on Climate Change	June 6, 2012. Last DOF reform 11-15-2023	Guarantee the right to a healthy environment and establish the concurrence of powers of the federation, federal entities and municipalities in the development and application of public policies for adaptation to climate change and the mitigation of emissions of greenhouse gases and compounds. .
Planning Law	January 5, 1983. Last reform DOF 05-08-2023	It establishes the basic rules and principles according to which the National Development Planning will be carried out and, based on it, the activities of the Federal Public Administration will be channeled.
Mining Law	June 26, 1992. Last reform DOF 05-08-2023	The law regulates article 27 of the Constitution on mining matters and its provisions are for public order and observance throughout the national territory. Its application corresponds to the Federal Executive through the Ministry of Economy, who is hereinafter referred to as the Secretariat. The exploration, exploitation, benefit and use of lithium is in charge, through the corresponding allocation, of the decentralized public body referred to in article 10 of this Law, sectorized to the Ministry of Energy.

Agrarian Law	February 26, 1992. Last reform DOF 04-25-2023	The Federal Executive will promote the comprehensive and equitable development of the rural sector by promoting productive activities and social actions with a gender perspective, aimed at increasing the well-being of the population and their participation in national life, under conditions of equality and parity.
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Source: Own elaboration with data from the official website of the Congress of the Union in Mexico.

At the State level, there is the “State Law for the Prevention and Mitigation of Climate Change and the programs “State Action Program against Climate Change of Baja California 2015 and 2012”.

Overall
 GHG Emissions
 Renewable Energy
 Energy Use*
 Climate Policy

1.5°C target is still alive, but just barely

Image 3.- CCPI 2023, data for Mexico

Source: Climate change performance index 2023.

In the previous description, the development was explained in terms of impact on the regulatory framework for Mexico in environmental matters, although the law indicates that intentional damage and deterioration to the environment is considered an extreme criminal sanction, which is observed in the latest national development plans of the upcoming six-year periods is a detriment to the actions or commitments on the part of the federal government, to the point of disappearing the environmental issue from the agenda in

the still current period of Andrés Manuel López Obrador, taking into account that it is already coming to an end, and the elected president Claudia Sheinbaum has announced to continue with the policy of her predecessor, this makes it clear what her position will be on the issue, however the expectation is high being the first woman in the executive branch of a democracy with legitimacy problems, which is why the environmental issue could have better positions on its scale of preferences once it assumes power.

Table 4

Description of Mexico's six-year national development plans in environmental matters.

Period	President	General politics	Environmental Policy
1970-1976	Luis Echeverría Álvarez	Political issues in gender equality Economic Policy: Measures labor policy agricultural development	No statement on environmental policy. It is only noted about the rapid development of industrialized countries.
1976-1982	José López Portillo y Pacheco	-Reaffirm and strengthen the independence of Mexico as a democratic Nation. - Provide the population with employment and minimum economic well-being, - Improve the distribution of income between people, production factors and geographic regions.	No statement on environmental policy.
1982-1988	Miguel de la Madrid Hurtado	-Preserve and strengthen democratic institutions -Overcome the crisis	No statement on environmental policy.

		-Recover growth capacity -Initiate the qualitative changes that the country requires in its economic, political and social structures.	
1988-1994	Carlos Salinas de Gortari	-The defense of sovereignty and promotion of the interests of Mexico in the world -The expansion of democratic life -Economic recovery with price stability -The productive improvement of the population's standard of living	No statement on environmental policy.
1994-2000	Ernesto Zedillo Ponce de León	-Strengthen the capacity of the State to guarantee our national security and -Recover political strength in the global economy. -Renew foreign policy to ensure a deep connection between Mexican communities, international financial stability, free trade, migration, democracy, human rights, drug trafficking, terrorism and care for the environment.	Promote international positions in line with internal transformations, with care for the environment
2000-2006	Vicente Fox Quesada	Guiding objective 1: improve the levels of education and well-being of Mexicans Guiding objective 2: increase equity and equal opportunities Guiding objective 3: promote education for the development of personal capabilities and individual and collective initiative Guiding objective 4: strengthen social cohesion and capital Guiding objective 5: achieve social and human development in harmony with nature Guiding Objective 6: Expand government response capacity to foster citizen trust in institutions	Guiding objective 5: achieve social and human development in harmony with nature Strategies to]. Harmonize the growth and territorial distribution of the population with the demands of sustainable development, to improve the quality of life of Mexicans and promote the balance of the country's regions, with the participation of the government and civil society. b]. Create an ecological culture that considers the care of the environment and the environment in decision-making at all levels and sectors. c]. Strengthen scientific and technological research that allows us to better understand ecological processes. d]. Promote sociocultural conditions that allow us to have environmental knowledge and develop aptitudes, skills and values to understand the effects of man's transformative action on the natural environment. Create new forms of relationship with the environment and promote sustainable production and consumption processes. e]. Achieve the protection and conservation of the most representative ecosystems of the country and its biological diversity, especially those species subject to some category of protection. F]. Stop and reverse pollution of water, air and soil. g]. Stop and reverse erosion processes and increase reforestation.
2006-2012	Felipe Calderon Hinojosa	Objectives and Strategies around five axes: 1. Rule of Law and security. 2. Competitive and job-generating economy. 3. Equal opportunities. 4. Environmental sustainability. 5. Effective democracy and responsible foreign policy.	Sets sustainable human development objectives. Where they stand out: 5. Reduce extreme poverty and ensure equal opportunities and the expansion of capabilities so that all Mexicans significantly improve their quality of life and are guaranteed food, health, education, decent housing and an adequate environment for their development as It is established by the Constitution.

			8. Ensure environmental sustainability through the responsible participation of Mexicans in the care, protection, preservation and rational use of the country's natural wealth, thus managing to strengthen economic and social development without compromising the natural heritage and the quality of life of future generations. Finally, this National Development Plan establishes that environmental sustainability requires that Mexico join with all efficiency and responsibility in international efforts to prevent the planet from suffering irremediable environmental dislocations, such as global warming.
2012-2018	Enrique Peña Nieto	Objectives and strategies around: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peace • Inclusion • Quality education • Prosperity • Global Responsibility 	Environmental policies of the six-year term IV.2. Action plan: eliminate obstacles that limit the country's productive potential To promote and guide inclusive and facilitating green growth that preserves our natural heritage while effectively generating wealth, competitiveness and employment. The economic incentives of companies and society must contribute to achieving a balance between the conservation of biodiversity, the sustainable use of natural resources and the development of productive activities, rewarding the owners or possessors of natural resources for the benefits of the environmental services they provide. Responsible management of water resources, increasing the coverage of drinking water, sewage and sanitation services, as well as hydro-agricultural and flood control infrastructure.
2018-2024	Andrés Manuel López Obrador	Focused on a discursive reconstruction of politics in Mexico. It is addressed in a very general way and mention is made of scholarship programs and strategic projects.	The environment is only mentioned on one occasion, highlighting the need for protection. No specific policy or objectives or goals are addressed in the entire document.

Source: Own elaboration with data from official sources of the national development plans for Mexico.

As can be seen from the six-year term of Ernesto Zedillo, a statement is made on the environment in accordance with the international context, hence in the following six-year term, which is characterized by a change of political party in power, it takes a drastic turn, highlighting a clear positioning on the environment and designing a set of objectives for the guiding axis of the environment.

The same thing happens with Calderón's six-year term, who, being from the same party, dedicates a lot of space to the issue, as well as the recognition that global warming is a problem that needs to be mitigated. Later there was a change of political party, however this period also recognized the problem and put it on the political agenda with what it called promoting green growth. However, in the current period and nearing its end, the issue is minimized and only the need for protection is raised, but without the design of clear objectives or lines of action.

Conclusions

Although in Mexico the advances are recognized in the regulatory framework and in the creation of administrative structures from the federal level, as well as

the recognition of the environmental issue in the Zedillo period, however the fact that in the current period that called itself the fourth transformation, has not been considered the environment like a priority issue, had in doubt its capacity of response. Given the global scenario that is demonstrated with the rise in temperatures increasing year after year, the rise in sea level that affects coastal areas in various ways, as well as the problem in the global food supply chain, all this seems not to be true. have importance for national politics in Mexico in the López Obrador period. However, it should be noted that Mexico has a wealth of natural resources which has generated a comfort zone for decision makers, not considering that resources may be scarce as indicated by economic principles.

In such a way that even with the problems of wealth distribution, they can afford to acquire vegetables and fruits at a low cost and even not consume them, luxuries that do not occur in Europe, for example. However, it would be thought that those who are most interested in protecting resources should be the decision makers themselves in the public sphere, however, as demonstrated with national development plans, actions

or commitments from the political level have increasingly decreased. Although the organizational structures have remained, the fact of not being part of a development plan limits the possibilities of creation in specific actions as has happened in recent years.

Even though there is a global consensus about the danger that exists in the survival of many societies, as well as the biological systems of the planet, countries like this one have not considered forceful actions that are reflected in national planning in the first instance. Another view on this problem in Mexico is the purely political aspect since although during the Foxist six-year term the objective "governing 5: achieving social and human development in harmony with nature" was dedicated to giving it continuity in the next six-year term of Felipe Calderon from 2006 to 2012, it is necessary to highlight that both former presidents represented the same political party, and that once these periods have ended and they experience a phase of political alternation, the approaches of the next government change and little by little the intensity of interest in them fades environment.

Returning to the basic idea of Olson (1965), who considers that "on a larger scale, social classes often give rise to thinking that they would act in the interest of the members", as has been demonstrated based on the official information for the case. In Mexico there has not been an interest in acting for the benefit of the common good in environmental matters. Surely this postulate can be valid in scenarios where the interests are merely economic, but it was not validated in aspects of survival and of the design of the politics.

With this I do not mean that Olson is wrong, but rather that an awareness is required about what the gain and risks would be, as happens in the struggles of social groups. However, on the environmental issue they seem to be avoiding the compelling aspects in policy, such as solar energy, management and rejection of solid materials, sustainable urban development, air pollution among others. For this reason, it is necessary to sow the

idea beyond the periods of government as well as partisan interests so that politics can be transformed and clear actions generated for the benefit of the common good and thereby contribute to the mitigation of environmental problems, taking into account that Mexico has participated and shown interest at the international level in issues of climate change and biodiversity, these interests must be reflected until reaching a local level in forceful actions.

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